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Prototype adjustable PM quadrupole and combined function magnets

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ABSTRACT

IFAST Task 11.3 has designed and built a prototype permanent magnet-based dipole-quadrupole magnet, referred to as the HEPTO magnet, as an energy saving alternative to an equivalent electromagnet. This report summarises the performance of the prototype with respect to the magnetic specification.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

The Hybrid Electromagnet-Permanent magnet Tuneable Optics (HEPTO) prototype has been designed and built in IFAST Work Package 11.3. The prototype is a permanent magnet device designed as a direct replacement for the electromagnet dipole-quadrupole combined function magnets designed for Diamond-II. Use of permanent magnets would facilitate a reduction in operating costs and carbon footprint.

The magnet design has been completed in order to meet the same magnetic field requirements in the same space envelope as the electromagnet. Unique features include mechanical shimming mechanisms, trim coils for field tuning and thermal shunts for improved temperature stability.

The target integrated gradient strength and field homogeneity were achieved using the mechanical shimming to adjust the field. The trim fields provide tuning of the field but are not as efficient as was originally predicted in the design. The relative change in field strength with temperature has been reduced through the use of thermal shunt material.

Future work will focus on improving the trim coil and thermal shunt designs. Work on increasing the technology readiness level will facilitate applying tuneable permanent magnet technology to future accelerators.

1 Introduction

The focus of IFAST Work Package 11 is the development of sustainable accelerator technologies to reduce the energy consumption and running costs of accelerator facilities.

The Hybrid Electromagnet-Permanent magnet Tuneable Optics (HEPTO) prototype combined function dipole-quadrupole (DQ) magnet has been designed and built as the deliverable of IFAST Task 11.3. The design of the HEPTO magnet aims to replace resistive electromagnetic coils with permanent magnets as the main source of the field in the DQ magnets for the Diamond-II storage ring upgrade in order to reduce the energy consumption of these magnets from 2.3 kW per magnet to a peak power consumption of 25 W. These magnets require independent tuning of the dipole and gradient fields for commissioning purposes. Hence, the hybrid design includes air-cooled trim coils for the field tuning.

The scope of this deliverable was to build the prototype magnet, and to demonstrate that it could meet the same magnetic field requirements as the equivalent electromagnet that has been designed for Diamond-II. Magnetic measurements of the built prototype have indicated that the specified integrated field strength and homogeneity have been achieved.

2 Design Overview

2.1 DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

The Diamond-II upgrade involves replacing the current double-bend achromat lattice with a multibend achromat in order to reduce the emittance of the electron beam and hence increase the brightness and coherence of the synchrotron radiation produced by the facility [1]. As part of this upgrade, the lattice requires 48 DQ magnets which act to simultaneously bend and focus the electron beam. A water-cooled electromagnet design has been completed as part of the Diamond-II technical design review. The nominal power dissipated by each of these magnets from electrical resistance alone is 2.3 kW. Water cooling circuits will increase the actual power consumption of the magnets. The aim of the HEPTO design is to achieve the same magnetic field parameters in the same physical space envelope, with a much reduced overall power consumption. This would reduce the running costs, and environmental impact of running the accelerator. The magnetic field requirements are summarised in Table 1.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Central dipole field	-0.6951	T
Central gradient	33.179	T/m
Effective dipole magnetic length	870	mm
Effective gradient magnetic length	850	mm
Integrated dipole field	-0.6047	T.m
Integrated gradient	28.1857	T
Bending radius	16.795	m
Good field region (GFR) radius	7	mm
Integrated field quality $\Delta B/B$ within GFR	5E-4	
Integrated multipoles	<1E-3	
Dipole tuning range	± 2.5	%
Gradient tuning range	± 2.5	%
Temperature stability (3°C range)	0.01	%

Table 1: Summary of magnetic field requirements.

2.2 MAGNET DESIGN

The design of the HEPTO DQ prototype is based on a single sided electromagnet dipole-quadrupole [2]. The design allows a combined function dipole-quadrupole field with high gradient to be achieved whilst being more efficient than an offset quadrupole design. Figure 1 shows an image of the Opera 3D [3] model of the design, with the key aspects labelled. The different colours represent

different materials and parts of the design. The permanent magnets (blue in Figure 1) are the primary sources of the magnetic field. By using permanent magnets instead of electromagnetic coils to generate the field, the power consumption of the magnet can be greatly reduced. The nominal power requirements of the equivalent electromagnetic DQs designed for Diamond II is 2.3 kW per magnet [1]. The permanent magnet blocks are magnetised as shown by the thick black arrows in Figure 1 to create the required dipole-quadrupole field. The magnetic blocks used in the design were originally purchased for building the modulator undulators for the Compact Linear Accelerator for Research Applications (CLARA) at Daresbury Laboratory. These undulators are no longer set to be built in the near future, so the permanent magnet blocks were repurposed for building of the HEPTO prototype. The material of all the magnet blocks is neodymium iron boron (NdFeB) grade 45M6 with a remanent field of $1.3 \text{ T} \pm 1\%$. The different magnet types (A, B, F) refer to blocks of different dimensions.

Figure 1: Labelled image of the Opera 3D model of the HEPTO prototype. Thick black arrows represent the direction of magnetisation of the permanent magnet blocks.

The yoke and poles (green in Figure 1) are made from Armco Iron soft magnetic steel so that the flux from the permanent magnets will flow through the yoke. The main and auxiliary poles are shaped so as to produce the desired dipole and quadrupole fields in the good field region whilst suppressing higher field harmonics. The pole tips are curved so that the dipole field on the beam axis is kept constant along the length of the magnet.

Thermal shunts (purple in Figure 1) have been included in the design to improve the stability of the design with respect to changes in environment temperature. These shunts are made from a Fe-Ni alloy with a negative temperature coefficient [4]. At a given temperature, a portion of the flux at the surface of the permanent magnets is diverted through the shunt, rather than through the magnetic yoke to the poles and across the bore. As the temperature increases, the remanent field of the permanent magnet decreases, but the saturation polarisation of the shunt also decreases. Therefore, at higher temperatures, less flux is shunted by the Fe-Ni alloy. If the thickness of the shunt is chosen correctly, the temperature effects can be made to balance so that a small change in temperature does not affect the magnitude of the dipole or quadrupole fields in the good field region. A target temperature stability of the field of $\pm 0.01\%$ over a 3°C temperature range (around a nominal temperature of 20°C) has been set because this level of stability is comparable to what can be achieved within power supply fluctuations of typical electromagnets [5]. Spare shunt material available in 0.5 mm thick sheets has been purchased from Soleil for the building of the HEPTO prototype. The magnetic model predicts an achievable temperature stability using the available material of $-0.056\%/^\circ\text{C}$. The cost of purchasing extra thermal shunt material to further improve the thermal stability was prohibitive for this prototype.

Trim coils (red in Figure 1) have been included in the design so that the field under normal operation can be fine-tuned. This will allow the nominal fields to be reached from permanent magnet blocks of finite size and magnetisation error. The coils must also be capable of being used to sweep the dipole and quadrupole fields independently over a range $\pm 2.5\%$ of the nominal values for use during commissioning. The coils are designed to be air-cooled to reduce the infrastructure and power requirements of the design compared to water-cooled coils.

2.3 MECHANICAL DESIGN

The mechanical design of the prototype has been completed by Kyma. Tuneability of permanent magnet devices is generally limited. Therefore, the strength and field quality of a built device is generally fixed. The mechanical design of HEPTO includes functionality to mechanically shim the positions of the main and auxiliary poles in order to adjust the field strength and homogeneity of the built magnet. This allows magnetisation and manufacturing tolerances to be loosened in the design, and accounted for in the built magnet. A photograph of the built magnet on the measurement bench at Daresbury Laboratory is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Photograph of the built HEPTO prototype magnet.

3 Magnetic Measurements

3.1 INITIAL MEASUREMENTS

The first set of magnetic measurements focussed on measuring the field strength and homogeneity of the prototype magnet before any mechanical shimming was applied.

Measurements were made using a Senis type H 3-axis Hall sensor and a 3MH3 Teslameter [6] to calculate the flux density vectors at a set of discrete points. The spatial resolution of the probe, as stated by the manufacturer, is $30 \times 5 \times 30 \mu\text{m}^3$ for the B_y (vertical) field component and $150 \times 10 \times 150 \mu\text{m}^3$ for the B_x (transverse) and B_z (longitudinal) field components. The planar Hall effect is suppressed through the application of the spinning current technique. The 3MH3 Teslameter provides an accuracy of up to 0.05% and a precision of 0.1 mT. The sensor was translated using a precision 3-axis motion system. The probe was mounted in a custom-designed 3D-printed holder. This holder was bolted to an extruded aluminium arm, which was connected to the motion stages. This motion system achieves 2 μm precision in the transverse (x) and vertical (y) planes and 5 μm precision in the axial plane (z) through the use of stepper motors and absolute encoders. The achieved

precisions are defined by an allowable tolerance set in the motion control software between the set and measured absolute position of the stages. The software polls the read position of the stages after sending a movement command. If the read position is not within the given precision set by the tolerance within a set time, a time-out error is raised. The set precisions have been found to be practical limits which allow large 3D scans to be performed without time-out errors being regularly raised. A granite bench provided vibration isolation to the probe. The Hall sensor was connected to the Teslameter through a CaH cable. The fields measured by the Teslameter were recorded by the control PC through a USB connection. Every point measurement of the field was recorded as an average of 100 samples recorded at a sample rate of 300 Hz. The HEPTO magnet was mounted on a granite bench, independent of the probe bench. The magnet was aligned parallel to the Hall-probe bench using a laser tracker to an accuracy of ± 0.075 mm over the full length of the magnet relative to all three axes of the Hall probe bench.

3.1.1 Centre-plane Fields

The first set of measurements focused on the central field qualities. Figure 3 shows a plot of the vertical (B_y) field component against the transverse (x) coordinate inside the 7 mm radius GFR, with the centre of the GFR ($x = 0$ mm) being set at the point where the field was equal to the nominal dipole field of -0.6951 T. The gradient measured by a linear fit to repeat plots was 32.972 ± 0.004 T/m. The gradient predicted by the Opera model was 33.179 T/m. The measured gradient was therefore 0.62% lower than the target value. This discrepancy may be due to the material properties of the magnetic steel, permanent magnet blocks and thermal shunts being slightly different to the modelled properties, or to small machining and assembly tolerances.

Figure 3: Plot of measured B_y field component vs transverse coordinate.

The magnetic field inside the GFR can be described by the field harmonics [7]. The harmonics in the central plane of the magnet can be measured by moving the Hall sensor in a circular arc in the transverse xy plane. A Fast Fourier Transform of the field vectors measured on the circular arc can be used to evaluate the field harmonics.

The field components were measured on the 7 mm radius of the GFR. The averaged dipole field from multiple scans was -695.17 ± 0.07 mT. The averaged gradient was 32.901 ± 0.005 T/m. The gradient measured using the harmonic method was lower than that determined from a linear fit to the transverse scans. This is likely because the harmonic scans account for other multipole field components, but the linear fits only account for a dipole and quadrupole field.

Figure 4 shows a plot of the measured real field harmonics normalised to the measured dipole field in the central plane. The plot also shows the normalised normal fields predicted from the Opera model. As can be seen from the plot, there is very good agreement between the measured and predicted harmonic fields from the Opera model.

Figure 4: Normalised real field harmonics in the central plane of the pre-shimmed magnet.

Figure 5 shows a plot of the measured skew field harmonics normalised to the measured dipole field. The plot does not show the skew harmonics for the Opera model as the model predicts no skew harmonics due to the symmetry of the model. The higher order skew harmonics ($n > 2$) are all below 0.1 %.

Figure 5: Plot of measured skew harmonic fields in centre plane of pre-shimmed magnet.

Boundary element methods (BEM) provide an alternative method of evaluating the fields in the GFR. If the field vectors normal to the boundary of a 3D volume are evaluated on all surfaces of the volume, BEM can be applied to reconstruct the 3D field vectors inside the volume. This method has several advantages over traditional point-by-point fields maps over large volumes. The method only requires measurements on the volume boundary, so much fewer measurements can be taken to evaluate the fields inside the volume. This allows for measurements to be completed in a shorter amount of time, minimising the impact of changes in ambient temperature on the measurements. Also, the method provides a magnetostatic solution to the fields, helping to minimise the impact of random measurement errors [8].

To provide a complimentary tool for evaluating the gradient in the centre of the magnet, a scan over a volume measuring $12 \times 12 \times 12 \text{ mm}^3$ was measured around the magnetic centre. The fields were reconstructed using BEM to find the gradient in the good field region. The scan was repeated three times to confirm the accuracy of the BEM calculations. The gradient was found to be $32.985 \pm 0.002 \text{ T/m}$. This is comparable to the gradient measured by harmonic analysis.

The normalised field homogeneity ($\Delta B/B$) is defined as the difference of the field in the good field region at a point to the nominal field at that point. The field homogeneity in the central plane has been determined through three separate techniques. The first is through a 6-th order polynomial fit to the data points measured by linear scans. The second is by re-constructing the fields in the good field region using the harmonic scans in the central plane. The third method is by reconstructing the fields in the central plane through the boundary element method. Figure 6 shows the homogeneity plotted in the central plane GFR as determined through these three methods and compares it to the homogeneity as calculated by the Opera model. All of the measurement methods show a generally good agreement with the homogeneity predicted by the Opera model. All measurement show an increase in the value of $\Delta B/B$ with distance from the magnetic centre. The homogeneity at the negative x (high field) side increases, then flattens out. The largest discrepancies are at the positive x (low field) side, where the homogeneity increases quickly. All of the measurement techniques predict

a larger value of $\Delta B/B$ near the edge of the GFR than the Opera model. This is likely due to the tolerances on the machining and positioning of the auxiliary poles.

Figure 6: Central field homogeneity $\Delta B/B$ of the pre-shimmed magnet recreated from a 6-th order polynomial fit to linear scans, multipole analysis of harmonic scans and BEM reconstruction.

Table 2 gives a summary of the main field components determined by the different methods and compared to the design parameters as determined using the Opera magnetic model. In all cases, the measured field gradient is lower than the design gradient predicted in the Opera model. It will be necessary to shim the magnetic to increase the gradient to the design value.

Model	Gradient / T/m	Maximum $\Delta B/B$
Opera	33.1791	1E-3
Polynomial fit	32.972 ± 0.004	$(1.7 \pm 0.2) E-3$
Harmonic analysis	32.901 ± 0.005	$(1.0 \pm 0.1) E-3$
BEM	32.985 ± 0.002	$(1.60 \pm 0.02) E-3$

Table 2: Summary of central plane field parameters of pre-shimmed magnet.

3.1.2 Integrated Fields

The integrated field components are the most relevant for describing the impact of the magnet on the electron beam. The magnet pole tips are curved in order to follow the machine bending radius of 16.795 m. Therefore, the dipole field component is expected to be constant along this curved beam trajectory in order to maintain a constant bending radius.

The integrated multipole field components have been evaluated by moving the Hall probe in circular arcs normal to the nominal reference trajectory and integrating the multipole fields evaluated at each

circular arc along the trajectory. The integrated dipole field measured by this technique was -0.6067 ± 0.003 T.m, which is stronger compared to the nominal value of -0.6047 T.m. The measured dipole effective length was 872.6 ± 0.1 mm, which is longer than the nominal value of 870 mm. This longer effective length accounts in part for the stronger than anticipated integrated dipole. This can be counter acted by a re-fiducialisation of the magnetic centre to a slightly weaker nominal dipole field of -0.6930 T in the magnet centre (or a transverse shift in magnetic centre of approximately $60 \mu\text{m}$).

The integrated gradient was measured as 28.070 ± 0.002 T, which is 0.41% weaker than the nominal value of 28.1857 T. This was expected given measured central gradient value was lower than the design value. The measured effective length of the gradient was 852.4 ± 0.1 m, which is again longer than the design effective length of 850 mm. This suggests a central gradient value of 33.066 T/m is required to reach the nominal integrated gradient of 28.1857 T.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the measured real and skew integrated field components along the reference trajectory respectively and normalised to the integrated dipole. Figure 7 also show the integrated real components normalised to the dipole as predicted by the Opera model. There is a good agreement between the measured and predicted integrated multipoles. All of the higher order integrated real multipoles are below the target of 0.1%, apart from the $n=4$ and $n=6$ multipoles. It was necessary to make these multipoles larger than 0.1% in the design to maintain the target integrated homogeneity of $5E-4$ in the GFR whilst achieving the target integrated gradient. Again, the Opera model predicts no integrated skew components due to symmetry. The integrated higher order skew components are all below 0.1%.

Figure 7: Integrated real multipole components of the pre-shimmed magnet.

Figure 8: Integrated skew multipole components of the pre-shimmed magnet

Figure 9 shows a plot of the first three real multipole field components measured along the reference trajectory. The dipole (b_1) and quadrupole (b_2) components are both constant through the main body of the magnet due to the curved pole tips. It can be seen that the effective magnetic length of the dipole is longer than the quadrupole, as was anticipated from magnetic modelling and seen in other combined function magnets [2]. Figure 9 also shows the sextupole (b_3) field component plotted along the reference trajectory. Spikes in the sextupole can be seen at either end of the magnet. The magnet has been designed with a non-zero sextupole through the length in order to cancel the end fields and minimise the integrated sextupole field. As can be seen from Figure 7, the measured integrated sextupole component is 0.021% of the integrated dipole. This is larger than the predicted value from the Opera model of -0.007%, but within the target of 0.1%..

Figure 9: Plot of measured multipole field components vs distance along reference trajectory.

A large volume boundary element scan was also performed through the whole length of the magnet. The fields reconstructed using this scan were used to evaluate the integrated dipole, gradient and field homogeneity. The BEM scan was used to find the magnetic centre of the magnet which gave the target integrated dipole field of -0.6047 T.m. This corresponded to a central dipole field of -693.0 mT and therefore an effective length of 0.8726 m, which is consistent with the effective length measured by the harmonic scans. The central and integrated gradients were found to be 33.000 T/m and 28.096 T respectively. These values are 0.3% and 0.09% larger than those predicted by the harmonic scans respectively. In general, the BEM predicts stronger fields than the harmonic scans.

Figure 10 shows a plot of the integrated field homogeneity calculated by reconstruction of the fields using the integrated harmonic scans and using the results of the BEM scan, and compared to the Opera model. As can be seen, there is good agreement in the predicted shape of the homogeneity from the harmonic and BEM scans. There is good agreement with the homogeneity predicted by the Opera model at the $-x$ (high field) side of the magnet. However, the agreement is not as good at the $+x$ (low field) end of the magnet. This is similar to the agreement seen for the central plane homogeneity measurements in Figure 6. The measured homogeneity exceeds the specified value of $5E-4$ at points beyond $x = 6$ mm. Therefore, the magnet does not meet the field quality requirements, and mechanical shimming must be implemented to improve the homogeneity.

Figure 10: Plot of integrated field homogeneity $\Delta B/B$ determined by reconstruction from integrated harmonic and BEM scans.

Table 3 summarises the main integrated field components calculated by the harmonic analysis and BEM and compares them to the model. The measured integrated gradient is less than the target value, and the homogeneity exceeds the target. Therefore, the mechanical shimming is intended to increase the gradient and to improve the homogeneity.

Model	Integrated gradient / T	Dipole effective length / m	Gradient effective length / m	Integrated $\Delta B/B$
Design	28.1857	0.870	0.850	$< 5E-4$
Harmonic analysis	28.070 ± 0.002	0.8726 ± 0.0001	0.8524 ± 0.0001	$(8.2 \pm 0.5)E-4$
BEM	28.096	0.8726	0.8515	$8.6E-4$

Table 3: Summary of integrated field parameters of the pre-shimmed magnet.

3.2 MECHANICAL SHIMMING

The mechanical design of the magnet accounts for expected material, machining and assembly tolerances by allowing small movement of the magnet poles to adjust the field. Given the measurements of the magnet, it is apparent that the integrated gradient was lower than the design value. The magnet can be mechanically shimmed to increase the gradient and to improve the homogeneity.

The magnet was shimmed iteratively by adjusting the vertical positions of the top main and auxiliary poles relative to the bottom main pole and measuring the integrated gradient strength and

homogeneity. The goal of the shimming was to achieve an integrated gradient within 0.1% of the nominal value, and the integrated homogeneity within the specification of $5E-4$. Figure 11 shows a plot of how the measured error in the integrated gradient relative to the target integrated gradient changed as a function of the mechanical shimming iteration. Before shimming, the measured gradient was 0.42% lower than the target value. By reducing the gap between the auxiliary poles in shimming iterations 1 to 3, the strength of the gradient was gradually increased, and the homogeneity at the low field end of the magnet improved. For shimming iterations 4 to 8 the gap between the main poles and the auxiliary poles was adjusted to maintain the homogeneity within the good field region, as well as minimising the error in the gradient. After 8 iterations, the measured integrated gradient was 28.196 ± 0.001 T, which is within 0.03% of the target integrated gradient. Therefore, the integrated gradient was brought within the target by the mechanical shimming.

Figure 11: Plot of integrated gradient error as a function of shimming iteration. The shaded region highlights the target difference from the nominal integrated gradient of $\pm 0.1\%$.

The maximum absolute integrated field homogeneity as a function of the shimming iteration is shown in Figure 12. Before shimming the maximum homogeneity was $8.2E-4$. After 8 iterations, the homogeneity was reduced to $2.7E-4$, which is within the target value of $5E-4$. Figure 13 shows a plot of the integrated homogeneity through the magnet as measured by integrating the harmonics along the reference trajectory before and after mechanical shimming.

Figure 12: Plot of maximum absolute integrated field homogeneity as a function of shimming iteration. The dashed line represents the target homogeneity of $5E-4$.

Figure 13: Integrated field homogeneity $\Delta B/B$ before and after mechanical shimming.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 show the multipole errors in the integrated real and skew field components respectively, compared to the design field components, for the magnet before and after shimming. The main differences between the pre-and and post-shimmed magnet harmonics are in the real and skew sextupole ($n=3$) and octupole ($n=4$). The shimming has resulted in a change in the normalised real skew from $(0.021 \pm 0.001)\%$ to -0.018% . This is within the target value of 0.1% after shimming.

Figure 14: Absolute errors in integrated real field components for different shimming iterations.

Figure 15: Absolute errors in integrated skew field components for different shimming iterations.

After the shimming iterations, the measured integrated real dipole and quadrupole were -0.6066 T.m and 28.196 T respectively. Through shimming, the measured integrated gradient was within 0.1% of the target, and the measured homogeneity was within the specification of 5E-4. Therefore, the mechanical shimming mechanism was extremely effective in adjusting the magnet to meet the specification. Table 4 summarises the main integrated field components before and after mechanical shimming.

	Dipole / T	Gradient / T/m	Integrated dipole / T.m	Integrated Gradient / T	Maximum ΔInt.B/Int.B
Design	-0.6951	33.1791	-0.6947	28.1857	<5E-4
Pre-shimming	-0.69517 ± 0.00007	32.901 ± 0.005	0.6067 ± 0.003	28.070 ± 0.002	(8.2 ± 0.5)E-4
Post-shimming	-0.6951 ± 0.0001	33.083 ± 0.008	0.6066 ± 0.0001	28.196 ± 0.001	(2.9 ± 0.1)E-4

Table 4: Summary of main field components before and after mechanical shimming.

3.3 TRIM COIL TUNING

The magnet also contains air-cooled trim coils which are required to allow independent tuning of both the dipole and quadrupole fields in the range $\pm 2.5\%$ in-situ for beam emittance measurements. The coils had been designed with a maximum current of 5 A to allow for air-cooling of these coils. Air-cooled coils provide a significant reduction in required infrastructure and operating costs compared to water cooled coils.

The coils were powered to different combinations of current in the range ± 5 A, and a harmonic scan about the magnetic centre in the central plane used to find the changes in the real dipole, quadrupole and sextupole fields. Figure 16 and Figure 17 show the percentage change in the dipole and quadrupole field components respectively with different combinations of currents in the trim coils. Figure 18 shows the absolute changes in the sextupole field harmonic with different trim coil currents. It is of note that the sextupole field component is nearly independent of the main coil current. Therefore, the auxiliary coil current can be used to adjust the integrated sextupole component of the magnet. The main coil can then be used to adjust either the dipole or quadrupole strength. This may be useful in the operation of the machine to dynamically adjust the integrated sextupole field.

Figure 16: Contour plot showing percentage change in central dipole field with trim coil currents.

Figure 17: Contour plot showing percentage change in quadrupole field with trim coil currents.

Figure 18: Contour plot showing sextupole field component measured in mT on the 7 mm GFR with trim coil currents.

A linear fit was used to predict the trim coil currents required to achieve a given combination of percentage changes in the dipole and quadrupole field. Table 5 summarises the currents required in each of the corrector coils to achieve the nominal fields in the two-dimensional plane and to achieve the desired tuning range for emittance measurements. It can be seen from the table that the predicted currents in the auxiliary coil exceed the current limit of 5 A required for air-cooling. The initial magnetic design had predicted that currents lower than 5 A would be required in both the main and auxiliary coils to achieve the tuning range. However, when the magnetic models were re-investigated to identify discrepancies, an error in the magnetic models was discovered. When this error was corrected, the predicted currents required to achieve the tuning range were in good agreement with those measured, as shown in Table 5. The corrected Opera model predicted that the main coils would be able to achieve the desired tuning range within the 5 A limit, but the auxiliary coils would require a current exceeding 5 A. For future work, the auxiliary coils would require more turns in order to provide a larger tuning range within the current limit. There is sufficient space in the current design to accommodate larger coils.

Change in dipole from nominal / %	Change in quadrupole from nominal / %	Required main coil current (predicted) / A	Required auxiliary coil current (predicted) / A
-2.5	0	-2.55 (-2.46)	-11.42 (-15.41)
+2.5	0	2.55 (2.46)	11.42 (15.41)
0	-2.5	-3.91 (-4.45)	11.44 (15.12)
0	+2.5	3.91 (4.45)	-11.44 (-15.12)

Table 5: Summary of coil currents required to achieve desired tuning range.

The maximum independent tuning ranges of the dipole and quadrupole fields with the current coil design can be determined by plotting the required coil currents against the tuning range, as shown for the dipole and quadrupole in Figure 19 and Figure 20 respectively. For independent tuning of the dipole field, a maximum tuning range of $\pm 1.1\%$ is achievable with the current coil design. For independent tuning of the quadrupole field, a tuning range of $\pm 1.1\%$ is also achievable. Therefore, the current design could still be used to vary the dipole and quadrupole fields independently, allowing for some emittance measurements to be performed.

Figure 19: Required trim coil currents as function of dipole tuning range for fixed quadrupole.

Figure 20: Required trim coil currents as function of quadrupole tuning range for fixed dipole.

The measurements of the tuning range using the coils highlight that the tuning of the field using coils is inefficient because the permanent magnet blocks effectively act as air gaps in the magnetic circuit. Therefore, the achievable field tuning range will always be limited. For the current design, the required tuning range of 2.5% is unachievable.

3.4 THERMAL STABILITY

The design of the magnet includes Fe-Ni thermal shunts to minimise the change in the field strength in the bore of the magnet with ambient temperature fluctuations. To measure the thermal stability of the magnet, the Senis type H probe was replaced by a type C probe and 3MH6 Teslameter [9]. The type C probe is capable of also recording the measured temperature of the probe, unlike the type H. The type H was used for the majority of measurements due to its smaller physical size, allowing measurements of the fields at all points within the magnet GFR.

The type C probe was mounted in the magnetic centre of the magnet. The dipole field and probe temperature were measured whilst the laboratory climate control system was used to vary the ambient temperature between 19°C and 21°C. Figure 21 shows the relative change in the measured field relative to the field measured at 20°C as a function of temperature and is compared to the expected change from the Opera model. By plotting a linear fit to all the measured points, the temperature stability was determined to be $(0.173 \pm 0.001) \text{ } \%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. From the Opera mode, the temperature stability was predicted to be $-0.056\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. The absolute change in field strength with temperature is larger for the measured magnet than was predicted. With no thermal shunts, the temperature stability was predicted to be $-0.209\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Therefore, the presence of the thermal shunts does reduce the change in field strength with temperature, compared to the magnet with no thermal shunts.

Figure 21: Measured relative change in dipole field with ambient room temperature relative to the field measured at 20°C.

The sign of the measured temperature stability is positive. This shows that the field strength increases with increasing temperature. This suggests that the thickness of the thermal shunt sections is larger than the optimum value for minimising the change in field with temperature. If fewer layers of thermal shunt material were used, the gradient in field change would be reduced, and the measured field strength would be increased.

The most likely cause for the discrepancy between the measured and predicted temperature stability is in the material behaviour of the thermal shunts. The exact BH material data of the thermal shunt material were not available. Instead, known data from a similar batch of material were used in the models. This result highlights the need to perform measurements of the BH data for the exact material to be used in building magnets and over the expected operational temperature range. This data is crucial for the accurate modelling of the magnets.

Another potential cause of discrepancy is in the temperature measurement. The recorded temperature was measured by the Hall probe electronics. This was assumed to be the ambient air temperature of the measurement environment. However, as the HEPTO magnet structure is a large volume of material, the actual temperature of the permanent magnet blocks and thermal shunt materials may change at a slower rate than the ambient air temperature. Therefore, measurements of the air temperature may not be fully indicative of the actual magnet temperature.

4 Conclusion

The HEPTO magnet prototype has been built and measured as part of IFAST task 11.3. The magnet was designed as an energy saving alternative to the electromagnetic design of the Diamond-II dipole-quadrupole magnets. The magnetic field is produced by permanent magnet blocks, as opposed to water-cooled coils. The challenge of making a fixed-field device has been mitigated with a shimming mechanism that allows the field strength and quality of the built device to be adjusted. Through this mechanical shimming, the target integrated dipole and quadrupole fields have been achieved within 0.01% and the target integrated field homogeneity of $5E-4$ has been met. This highlights that that same magnetic field parameters can be achieved with a permanent magnet device. Therefore, 110 kW plus water cooling power could be saved in the routine operation of the Diamond-II machine if all 48 electromagnet DQs were replaced with HEPTO magnets. This would provide a significant saving in both operating costs and carbon footprint of the facility.

Future work should focus on understanding discrepancies between the magnetic models and the built magnet. These include improvements in the trim coil design to improve the achievable field tuning range from 1.1% to match the requirement of 2.5% tuning. Also, testing of thermal shunt materials to lead to improved design of the temperature compensation circuit would allow for improved thermal stability of the magnet.

The use of permanent magnets as replacements for electromagnets provides an attractive option for reducing the environmental impact of accelerator operations. The focus of future projects will be on developing the technology readiness level of tuneable permanent magnets so that this technology can be widely adopted in future accelerator facilities to reduce the operating power of beamline magnets.

5 References

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6 Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
$\Delta B/B$	Normalised field homogeneity
DQ	Dipole magnet with transverse gradient (quadrupole field)
GFR	Good field region
HEPTO	Hybrid Electromagnet-Permanent magnet Tuneable Optics